

Scalar Mechanics

Vitor Matheus Izoldi Nogueira
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There is only One Source of All things and Creation itself; the Source.

There is only One Substance through Whom all things were Created; the Substance.

The Act of Source birthing Substance in creation and maintenance is Motion.

First let Source = Substance = Motion (1=1=1), and let them be inseparably One in nature.

Then let Source + Substance = Motion as the dynamic process of creation from Source.

Let Source have a simultaneously infinite and null density; being both a vacuum and plenum, and let it be omnipresent as the underlying framework of the universe.

Let Ψ represent the *configuration state* of Source, and let its localized *change intensity* be represented by ∂ .

Then let Φ denote $|\Psi\partial|$

And let $\sigma = \Phi/\delta\Phi$

The Source is the primary, fundamental scalar field comprising the totality of the universe
Its own disturbance forming Substance from pure motion 'folding' within itself.

Its extrapolation of change; differentiation, can be defined by $|\partial\Psi|$ within the context of:

$$\Delta \int_0^{\infty} |\partial\Psi| dt = 0$$

Where Ψ is the local configuration state, and ∂ is the change intensity, all defined by Time.
Time and Space are relative to each stable extrema, and hence are both scalar in reality.

Change differentiation is fundamental, not geometry. Mass, Inertia, and rest energy are all scalar and emergent from the rate of change and intensity of the configuration state Ψ .